

MODELLING OF COMPRESSION MOULDING PROCESS CYCLE TIME AND APPLICATION OF DFMA CONCEPT TO EVALUATE THE TOOLING COSTS FOR CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES T-SHAPE PARTS

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ABSTRACT

In order to help the engineering teams to make the decision to produce new aircrafts parts using a new manufacturing technology, it is important to be able to predict the manufacturing costs early at the design stage. A new cost analysis model composing of different modules for calculating cost elements to predict the manufacturing costs of two compression moulding processes for carbon fibre thermoplastic composites was proposed [1]. The tooling costs were already estimated by the same authors using the DFMA concept for these two processes [2]. This present study aimed, on one hand, at estimating the mould costs, and on the other hand, at predicting the cycle time of a compression moulded carbon/PEEK composite T-shape part made of short fibre randomly oriented prepreg strands. The machining costs and the assembly costs of the mould were estimated using respectively DFM and DFA modules of the DFMA commercial software of Boothroyd and Dewhurst Inc. For the simulation of the process cycle time that included the heating and cooling times the commercial COMSOL software was used. The simulated process cycle time and the estimated mould costs were then compared with experimental results conducted in a research manufacturing laboratory [3]. It was found that the cycle time calculated by the numerical modelling was validated and the estimated mould costs are close to that of workshop.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the aerospace industry became more competitively interested in developing the compression moulding process of structural parts made of carbon fiber thermoplastic composites as a new manufacturing technology due to short cycle time, important material weight reduction and ability to form complex geometries with large production volumes at lower costs. Therefore, in order to help the engineering teams to make the decision to produce new parts, it is important to be able to predict the manufacturing costs using cost estimation models early at the design stage. In fact, there are several available models for estimating the manufacturing costs of composites materials but they were limited to some specific process and required experimental studies. Furthermore, the cost analysis data for thermoplastic composite parts manufactured by compression moulding are almost nonexistent. A new cost analysis model composing of different modules for calculating cost elements to predict the manufacturing costs of two compression moulding processes for carbon fibre thermoplastic composites was proposed. This model was based on industrial and academic research data, which included process parameters such cycle time, material dimensions, production volume, etc. and also infrastructure costs such as material price, labor rate, capital costs, equipment depreciation, tooling price, energy price, administration costs, etc.

This present study aimed at simulating numerically the compression moulding cycle time for manufacturing composite T-shape parts using commercial COMSOL software and at estimating The T-shape mould costs by DFMA softwares of Boothroyd and Dewhurst Inc.

2 COMPRESSION MOULDING PROCESS OF T-SHAPE PART[3]

The studied part was a T-shape of 82 mm x 25 mm x 3,17 mm rib cavity (figure 1c) made of discontinuous fibre strands, that were slit manually or automatically from unidirectional prepreg tape. These strands were placed in the mould cavity and distributed in such a way to assure their random orientation (figure 1a). The experimental set up of manufacturing T-shape is shown in figure 1b:

Figure 1 a) Cavity Mould filled with ROS. b) Experimental set up. c) ROS T-shape part [3]

2.1 Heating step

After the placement of the material in the cavity mould which was assembled with two inserts and frames, the mould was transferred afterwards to a 250 kN MTS press mounted with two H-13 steel platens of 101.6 mm × 101.6 mm. The platens were heated using four heating cartridges and controlled by two auto-tuning PID controllers. An initial pressure of 10 bars was applied during heating. When processing temperature was reached, a pressure of 30 bars was applied for a dwell of 15 minutes and during cooling step. Two thermocouples used to measure the temperature of the material during the cycle were inserted through the mould.

2.2 Cooling step

At the end of the heating step the mould the part started to cool down from 380°C to ambient temperature at a rate of 10 °C/min using compressed air flowing through cooling channels in the mould platens. Afterwards, the cooled plate was removed.

3 HEAT TRANSFER PROCESSES

The conduction and convection heat transfer mechanisms are presented in figure 2. In order to calculate the conduction heat transfer between the ROS T-shape part, the platens and the mould, these

components were considered as semi-infinite solids in contact with no internal heat generation. The transient temperature distribution versus the heating time in the whole compression moulding system including the platens, the moulds, the ROS T-shape part was determined using the following differential equation (1):

$$\rho_i c_{pi} \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (k_i \nabla T) + Q_s \quad (1)$$

where ρ_i , c_{pi} , k_i were respectively the density, the specific heat capacity, the thermal conductivity of the considered materials ($i = 1,2$) and Q_s was the volume heat source. The thermal and physical proprieties of the steel material were obtained directly from the database of the COMSOL[®] software. The thermal and physical proprieties of the materials are presented in table 1.

Figure 2 Contact heat transfer mechanisms

Proprieties	Unit	Materials	
		$i = 1$	$i = 2$
		CF/PEEK	Steel
Density	(kg/m ³)	1540	7850
Specific heat	J.kg ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹	1320	475
Thermal conductivity	W.m ⁻¹ .K ⁻¹	0.75	44,5

Table 1 Physical and thermal properties of the materials [4]

In this study the contact resistance effects were neglected at the interface between the solids. In order to assure the uniformity of the temperature throughout the composite part the desired temperature has to be maintained at 380°C for a given time. During this dwelling period the power density applied to the heating cartridges has to be reduced to an adequate value. In considering the boundary conditions, external convective heat transfer occurred between the platens, the mould, and the air according to the following formula (3): $k_i \Delta T = h(T_{air} - T)$ (2) where h is the heat transfer coefficient for natural convection, T_{air} the air temperature assumed to be constant at 20°C.

In the cooling step, the air was flowed in the cooling channels through cylindrical drilled holes inside each platen. The velocity and the temperature of the air were considered to be constant.

4 NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS

4.1 Heating step simulation

The heating step included two periods: heating and dwelling. The heating period was simulated using the transient thermal analysis module of the commercial COMSOL[®] Multiphysics[®] software to solve numerically all the heat transfer equations formentioned basing on the 3D finite elements method. The model composed of two platens, the frame, the two inserts, two plates mould, the ROS T-shape and insulators. These components were considered as solid blocks in contact. The model included also 4 cylindrical heating cartridges with radius of 3,834 mm and 101,6 mm length inserted in each platen. Figure 3 shows the geometry of the model for simulation of heating process.

Figure 3 The geometry of the model for heating process geometry

Figure 4 The mesh of the model geometry for heating simulation

The time-dependent study was selected in order to access the evolution of temperature in the ROS T-shape by steps of time. The heating time to reach the temperature of 380°C was defined in the range from 0 to 2730s with a step of 5s.

The boundary thermal conditions during the heating stage were as follows: for the convective heat transfer the initial value of air temperature was fixed to 20°C; the initial value of temperature in the whole model was fixed to 25°C; the necessary heat source rate at the surfaces of heating cartridges was adjusted using the following formula: $56000 \cdot (T < 380[\text{degC}]) + 16000 \cdot (T > 380[\text{degC}])$. So, the necessary power density applied to the heating cartridges to reach processing temperature (380°C) was 56000 kw/m² and to attain the temperature uniformity throughout the part the necessary power density was 16000 kw/m² (the dwelling period); the upper surface of higher platen and the lower surface of the bottom platen were insulated. The processing geometry model was meshed with free tetrahedral elements. Figure 4 shows the mesh of the model geometry for heating simulation.

The geometry characteristics of the heating model are presented in the table 2:

Domains		Nature	Dimensions (x,y,z) (mm)	Position (x,y,z) (mm)
Platens	Bottom	Steel block	101,6 x 101,6 x 22,62	(0,0,39.88)
	Top			(0,0,-36.71)
Cavity mould		Steel block	101,6 x 101,6 x 50,8 Thickness : 9,58	(0,0,0)
Punch		Steel block	82,44 x 82,44 x 9,58	(0,0,23.42)
Mould plate	Bottom	Steel block	101,6 x 101,6 x 5,36	(0,0, -50.7)
	Top			(0,0,53.87)
ROS T-shape part		2 Solid block (CF/PEEK)	Flange : 82,44 x 82,44 x 3,17 Rib : 82,44 x 25,4 x 3,17	(0,0,17.4) (0,0,3.12)

Insulators (2)		Top	101,6 x 101,6 x 19,74	(0,0,66.42)
		Bottom	101,6 x 101,6 x 19,74	(0,0,-63.25)
Heating cartridges (8)	Bottom	Steel solid cylinder	r = 3,834 mm, L = 101,6 mm	(-10.16,-50.8, -31.15) (-30.48,-50.8, -31.15) (10.16,-50.8, -31.15) (30.48,-50.8, -31.15)
	Top			(-10.16,-50.8, 34.32) (-30.48,-50.8, 34.32) (10.16,-50.8, 34.32) (30.48,-50.8, 34.32)

Table 2 The geometry characteristics of the heating model

4.2 Cooling simulation

For cooling stage, the cooling channels were added to the geometry of the model, which were connected to drilled cylindrical holes. The model geometry of the cooling system is shown in figure 5:

Figure 5 The model geometry of the cooling system

The geometry model characteristics for simulation of the cooling step are presented in the table 3:

Domains	Nature	Dimensions (mm)		Position (x,y,z) (mm)	
		Radius	Length		
Cooling channels	Machined cylindrical holes	3,834	101,6	Bottom	(-50.8,0,-40.73)
					(-50.8,34.5,-40.73)
					(-50.8,-34.5,-40.73)
				Top	(-50.8,0,43.9)
					(-50.8,34.5,43.9)
					(-50.8,-34.5,43.9)

Table 3 The geometry characteristics of the cooling model

The finite element mesh of the model for cooling stage comprised free tetrahedral elements with finer size. The cooling time was defined in the range from 0 to 2000 seconds with a step of 5 seconds to cool down from 380°C to ambient temperature. The boundary thermal conditions during the cooling step were as follows: the initial value of temperature in the whole model was fixed to 380°C; the heat source was stopped. The upper surface of higher platen and the lower surface of the bottom platen were insulated. The velocity of the water was 50 m/s.

5 EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL RESULTS

The distribution of the calculated temperature throughout the model at heating times of 30 and 1600 seconds are presented in figures 6 and 7 respectively. The distribution of the calculated temperature throughout the model at cooling times of 20 and 1800 seconds are presented in figures 8 and 9 respectively.

Figure 6 The distribution of temperature in the model at heating time of 30 s

Figure 7 The distribution of temperature in the model at heating time of 1600 s

Figure 8 The distribution of temperature in the model at cooling time of 20 s

Figure 9 The distribution of temperature in the model at cooling time of 1800 s

The obtained numerical results of the transient temperature for the present model were compared to experimental data [5]. Figure 10 shows the comparison between experimental temperatures and the numerical inside the ROS T-shape part.

Figure 10 Comparison between numerical and experimental temperatures inside the ROS T-shape part

6 MOULD COSTS ESTIMATION

In order to make the cost analysis of the moulds using the DFMA softwares for T-shape mould, the material selected is the P20 steel from metaux solutions Inc. The proprieties of the mould material are presented in table 4.

Propriety at 20 C	Units	Value
Density	Lb/in ³	0,283
Thermal conductivity	W/m.K	34
Specific heat	J/Kg.K	460
Modulus of elasticity	MPa	890 – 1030 ^a

^a According to EN 18265, scale B2

Table 4 Proprieties of the mould material [6](Adapted)

6.1 T-shape mould manufacture processing

The T-shape mould was manufactured at two places: The platens and mould plates were machined in AMTC, whereas the inserts, the frame were made in Mc Gill University. It composed of two main parts: the punch and the cavity, the punch consists of upper male platen, upper plate. The cavity includes inserts, frame, and bottom platen and bottom plate. The mould manufacturing process is divided into two steps: The first step is to cut parts from a rectangular bar stock. The second step consists to cut and remove material from the parts. For making all the mould components, it is necessary to use milling and drilling operations. The rough and finish face milling machine was used to make features such as faces and insert rib. The drilling operation consists to drill holes in all the components followed by reaming, tapping or counter drilling operations for securing and to set up the heating cartridges, the thermocouples, and the cooling system in the platens. After the machining operations, all the surfaces of the mould were polished and inspected afterward.

6.2 T-shape mould assembly processing

After machining and polishing, the mould was assembled by socket head cap screws, dowel pins and checked to make sure the mould components fit together properly, then the mould and the insulators were fixed to the die set as shown in figure 11.

Figure 11 Mould fixture [3]

DFMA costs estimation results: The mould cost results obtained by DFMA program for the T-shape mould are presented in Table 5.

Mould components	Manufacturing cost/part	Assembly cost/part(\$)	Repeat count	Total costs(\$)
Frame A	212,73	9,83	2	445,12
Frame B	238,18	9,84	2	496,04
Insert with rib	176,69	3,95	1	180,64
Insert without rib	141,57	4,04	1	145,61
Top platen	416,18	10,82	1	427
Bottom platen	351,04	10,82	1	361,86
Top plate	189,65	7,375	1	197,025
Bottom plate	189,65	7,375	1	197,025
Dowel pins for cavity	9,32	5,675	-	14,995
Dowel pins for punch	3,72	2,655	-	6,375
S.H.C screw for cavity	6,36	9,605	-	15,965
S.H.C screw for punch	1,88	2,265	-	4,145
Cavity	1776,45	80,805	1	1857,255
Punch	611,43	23,115	1	634,545
T-shape mould	2387,88	103,92	1	2491,8

Note: the labor rates used in the DFM and DFA softwares are respectively Cad \$85/hour and Cad 30\$/hour

Table 5 T-shape mould estimated costs

T-shape mould costs breakdown: Figure 12 presents the costs breakdown of T-shape mould.

Figure 12 Costs breakdown of T-shape mould

DFMA and workshop cost estimation comparison for the T-shape mould: (Table 6)

Item	DFMA	Workshop
Manufacturing costs (\$)	2387,87	-
Assembly costs (\$)	103,93	-
Design costs (\$)	450	-
Total costs (\$)	2941,8	3000

Table 6 Workshop and DFMA T-shape mould costs estimation comparison

7 CONCLUSIONS

For the heating step, the model predicted almost the same temperature throughout the T-shape part. However, there was an average difference of around 15% between the simulated and experimental temperatures through the thickness of the ROS T-shape part.

There was no significant difference in the heating time to reach the consolidated temperature of 380°C from the ambient temperature of 25°C, between the numerical and experimental results. The

experimental heating time was approximately 43 minutes whereas the simulated heating time was about 46 minutes.

For the dwelling period, the average error between the simulated and experimental temperatures was around 2%.

For the cooling step, the average error between the numerical and experimental temperatures was approximately 1,5%. The experimental cooling time (77 minutes) was approximately the same as that obtained by the numerical simulation (80 minutes).

In overall, the cycle time including the heating and cooling steps estimated by the numerical modelling for a compression moulded carbon/PEEK composite T-shape part was validated. In fact, there was around 4% of error between the simulated and experimental time.

The mould costs results showed that the mould cavity costs are very higher than the punch mould costs because the cavity needs more components to make than the punch.

The T-shape mould costs estimated by DFMA softwares are close to that of workshop. The error between them is about 2%.

Based on obtained cost results for the T-shape mould by DFMA costs estimating softwares, the mould costs extrapolation can be applied for other mould similar geometries by changing thickness or area of mould.

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